

THE SPREAD OF SUFISM IN MOVAROUNNAHR DURING THE PERIOD OF TIMURI AND THE PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THEIR SECTS

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Abstract: The article examines the development of Sufism during the Timurid period and the theoretical and methodological problems of its research, the interpretation of the perfect human being in the Sufi-philosophical views of the Sufis of the Timurid period, the significance of the views of the thinkers of the Timurid period regarding the education of the perfect person. Also, during the Timurid era, the spread of Sufism in Movarounnahr and its sects were analyzed philosophically.

Key words: Timurids, mystic, mysticism, thinker, perfect human being, order, spiritual maturity, perspective, social protection, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, concept.

INTRODUCTION. When it comes to Sufism, people who are aware of the state of peoples and the characteristics of their society immediately come to mind with the idea of internal spiritual changes, the phenomenon of alienation from the total things related to worldly life. Such a trend existed in one form or another in many nations. However, the word "mysticism" is associated with deep and complex processes that appeared in the Indian peninsula. And even today it is impossible to understand the mysterious and complex rich culture of India without understanding Indian "mysticism". Although a very deep study of Indian culture leads to nothing but admiration, it is difficult to understand Sufism without paying attention to the monasticism associated with the spread and development of Christianity.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. A. Arberry, W. Jones, D. Malcolm, J. Graham, Mir Waliddin, Wilcox Linn, (England), K. Ernst (USA), I. Goldsier (Hungary), K. Snook-Heurgronje (Netherlands), Louis Massignon, J.G. Tassi (France), Alfred von Kremer, Fried August Toluk, Y. Hammer and F. Rueckert, Jürgen Paul, Annemarie Schimmel (Germany), YE.E. Bertels, A.M.Bagautdinov, I.S.Braginsky, A.Krimsky, V.Zhukovsky, I.Petrushevsky, A.D.Knish, ET.Sovitova, (Russia), K.Kodirov, D.Kh.Fayzaliyev, D.M.Takheri, K.S.Abdurakhimov (Tajikistan), I.Mo Minov, M. Hazratkulov, Kh. Alikulov, O. Boriyev, Hamidjon

Hamidiy, N. Komilov, Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf, G. Navro'zova, O. Usman, H. Boltaboyev, R. Shodiyev, J. Kholmuminov , B. Nomozov, D. Sayfullayeva, Kh. Samatov, F. Muzaffarov, V. Cho'liyeva and others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Greek philosophy has similarities with later philosophical movements. We mean the mysterious ideas of Epicurus and Orpha. In addition, it is possible to dwell on the philosophy of navaplotunists, especially Plotinus. It is not difficult to feel the influence of their ideas in the ceremonies of Irfan and Tariqat.

Sufism, like other spiritual and spiritual phenomena of human life, has experienced extremism and weakness. But the general similarities of these events can be described as follows:

The main task of Sufism is to give an empirical meaning to existence, to get rid of its external appearance (image), that is, to choose a psychological and practical method that helps to find the spiritual and spiritual truth that is beyond emotions and reason. . In the end, Sufism claims to merge with the whole divine being, to melt and merge with the supreme truth of the universe.

The author of the book "Awariul Maarif" writes: "Sufis are named after the woolen clothes they wear, some say that they wear woolen clothes to protect their private parts. Sufis strive to get rid of the people of the world, those who are satisfied with the little food that is enough for life, and those who are busy in the observation of other, divine-spiritual life. They did not care about sensual pleasures, because their hearts were always occupied with the Supreme Truth, and they focused all their strength and will on life in the other world. This assumption (the idea that Sufism arose from the word Suf) is linguistically correct, because whoever wears woolen clothes is called a Sufi.

There are several views on the etymology of the words Sufi and Sufism. One of the great mystics of our country, N. Komilov, writes: "Some say that this word comes from the word "rank", because a Sufi is one who stands in the first line of those who have entered the path of God. Some scholars say that it is derived from the word "suffa": the Companions of Suffa are pious people who left the world during the lifetime of the Prophet, and they explain that Sufis imitate them. Another group of scholars said that the word Sufi comes from the word "safa", because the heart of this category shines like the sun of sidqu safa. Others write that Sufism is derived from the word "sufuh", and Sufuh is the conclusion of something. They called them Sufis because this community was the conclusion of the people.

There are those who say that the word Sufi comes from the word "pure". Abu Rayhan Beruni in his "Asorul Bakiya" shows that this word is derived from the Greek word "suf". But many believe that the word Sufi is derived from the Arabic word "suf". The dictionary meaning of the word "suf" is wool and cloth woven from wool. Sufis are called "wool-clothed" (Persian "pashminaposh") because they often wear woolen cloaks or sheepskin coats. In our opinion, this next etymological meaning is closer to the truth, because the word Sufi is formed from the word "suf" according to the rules of the Arabic language.

There are also those who say that the origin of this term is derived from the name of Sufa ibn 'Udd ibn Tobiha, who became famous for his frequent prayers during the Jahiliyyah period. However, there are researchers who believe that this interpretation is not acceptable because it is not possible to take as an example people of a religion other than Islam.

Another quote from the book "Avoriul Maarif":

"They are called Sufi because they are in the first place in the sight of God... And they say again that the first form of this istilah was "Safawi" and gradually became "Sufi" because it was difficult to pronounce... Another the idea is that "sufi" is derived from the word "sufa" (supa), because in the time of the prophet (pbuh), there were poor immigrants who lived on the sufa, so they were called "people of the sufa" . Even if this idea is incorrect from the point of view of linguistic rules, it is consistent from the point of view of meaning.

And he adds: "There was no such custom during the Prophet's time, it corresponds to the time of the subjugated people. It is narrated from Hasan Basri that he said: I saw a Sufi while circumambulating the Kaaba and offered him help. He said to me: "I have four coins. This also confirms what Sufyan said: "If Abushim was not a Sufi, I would never have understood the meaning of hypocrisy. They said that this istilah ("Sufi" term) was not used until the year 200. And about the specific characteristics of this category, the author of "Avoriul Maarif" writes after enumerating the sensual desires that lead enlightenment to darkness: people of this category who are bound have left the world and are shunned from people, choosing to be happy. They would have some kind of slum corner, where they would gather and talk, and sometimes each of them would be treated separately. These people learn from the people of Sufa. Relinquishing worldly opportunities, they seek the presence of the Lord and as a result, due to their meritorious deeds, they attain enlightenment through duty, attain enlightenment through duty, learn the language of divine secrets. As Haris said: "I sat awake until dawn and realized the essence of faith."

Thanks to this, they gained high enlightenment and knowledge and became the owners of special morals. And then they began to use special terms and words that only they understood in their meaning.

All this was passed down from the big to the small, and it became a strict tradition. And these names became a picture among them and settled in this way. And these names and terms express their awareness of God's enlightenment, their mystical knowledge, their self-control, slogans, truths and secrets discovered about the Truth.

However, Henry Corbin, noting that the word "Sufi" is derived from the Arabic word "suf", suggests that it is derived from another word, which in our opinion is more plausible: "The term is from the Greek "zorpoz". The opinion that it is a modified form of the word "(wise or learned)" is reliable and seems... Beruni drew attention to it in the fourth century of the Hijri, but not all orientalist unanimously accepted this assumption. .

"Although the letter ("sin") in the word "zorpoz" has been replaced by the letter ("sod") in the word "sufi", this letter has been preserved in the word "philosopher". If this assumption is correct, we will have to pay attention to the extraordinary talent of Arab linguists, because they find a Semitic root for a word borrowed from abroad.

When did this istilah, which appeared in Arabia in the early Islamic times, enter Movarounnahr and Khurasan? The first tabaqat books written about Sufis: "Kitab al-ta'arruf 'ala mazhab ahl al-tasawuf" by Kalabadi from Bukhara (v. 380/990-384/994), "Kitab al-lum" by Sarraj (v. 988) fi-t-tasawwuf", Sulami's (v. 1021) "Tabaqat al-Sufiya", Qusayri's (v. 465/1074) "Ar-risala fi ilm at-tasawwuf", Hujwiri's (approx. v. 1071) "Kashf al -mahjub" works, many Movarounnahr and Khurasan mystics appear under the name of "Sufi".

At the same time, it should be noted that al-Hakim al-Tirmizi (approx. v. 932), who is mentioned under the name "Sufi" in all these works, once used the word "Sufi" or "Tasawwuf" in his work "Nawadir al-Usul". we did not meet. In the work, the phrase "fwşrla sbri" (he wears wool on the path of asceticism) is used several times. But people who wear wool are not called "Sufi".

According to Sulam's "Tabaqat al-Sufiya" work: "Ja'far al-Khuld (d. 348/959), the collector of Sufi divans, said: "I have more than 130 divans of Sufis," then Husayn ar-Razi followed him. said: "Do you have any books of Al-Hakim at-Tirmidhi?" - when asked, he said: "I do not consider him one of the Sufis." Also, al-Ansari of Herat (d. 481/1089) in his work "Tabaqat al-Sufiya"

written in the dialect of Herat, wrote about Abu Bakr al-Warraq at-Tirmizi (d. 906-7): "Hakim, who was a scholar, non-Sufi, Sufi is something else," he says.

Also, in the work "Tarikh Naysobur" by al-Hakim al-Naysoburi (d. 404/1014), information is given about the scholars and sheikhs of Nishapur in the 9th-10th centuries. The work mentions 50 famous mystics of Nishapur. But they are not called by the name "Sufi", but by the names "zahid", "abid", "voiz", "muzakkir". Abu Bakr al-Wasiti (d. 320/932) is the first to be called a "Sufi" in this work. Abu Bakr al-Wasiti lived in Nishapur for a long time, but he was originally from Baghdad, and in his youth he attended the circle of the famous mystic Junayd Baghdadi (d.910). Abu Bakr al-Wasiti was a prominent representative of Iraqi Sufism, who contributed to the spread of Iraqi Sufism in Khorasan. This is the reason why he got the name "Sufi".

Also, when the famous Jerusalem geographer and traveler Abu Abdullah al-Maqdisi (d. 380/990) wrote about Khurasan mystics in his work "Ahsan al-Taqasim fi marifati aqalim", he did not call them "Sufi" but "obid" and "hermit"., called "preacher".

In the first centuries of the Hijri, the Muslim mystics of Movarounnahr and Khurasan were not called "Sufi". But in the sources of the later period, they were completely "Sufi" or, to be more precise, the name "Sufi" was attached to them. So, in the early Hijri centuries, the term "Sufi" was not applied to all mystics. This name was mainly used in relation to the people of the school of Sufism in Baghdad and in general in Iraq. That is why some medieval scholars divided mystics into "Sufis" and others. What is the reason for this separation? Were there any conflicts between these two schools?

Sufologist N.Komilov: "If the word "suf" is derived from the word "suf", in turn, the words "mystic", "mustasuf", "muttasuf", "mutasawwif" are derived from "sufi". formed. Mustasuf is a word used to refer to people who pretend to be Sufis, but whose real goal is to pursue career and wealth. are people who could not rise to the level of fiy. Sufis are considered to be Sufis who are inclined to Sufi ideas at heart, who have taken Sufism as their faith, but who have not undergone the practice of Tariqat, and who are not officially Sufis.

Husayn Voiz Koshifi divided the Sufis into three groups in his work entitled "Futuvvatnamai Sultani": modernists, mutarasms, and scholars. Contributors are fans and friends of the people of the sect. They look at the dervishes with love, participate in their conversation, perform their services, and consider themselves partners in the merit. The meaning of the word "mutarasm" is those who follow the customs and rituals of dervishes, but although they outwardly

imitate the customs of dervishes, they are inwardly demanding and hope to enjoy divine favor due to their devotion to this category.

Scholars - those who have reached the truth, they can be described as Sufis of high rank. Real saints, sheikh murshids grew out of them.

Most of the people of Sufism who lived in Khurasan found the views of Sufism that prevailed in Iraq to be "formal" and did not reveal Sufism outwardly, but believed that it should live only in the heart. those who claim that it is a joke. These mystics considered it a hypocrisy to separate themselves from the society and live in a separate group by building houses, wearing special clothes, and organizing open zikr meetings. That is, Khorasan mystics prioritized the inner over the outer. On the other hand, the mystics of Khorasan and Mowarounnahr paid too much attention to the subject of the self (for example, blame, they looked for faults and defects in the self and sought to blame themselves), and were criticized by the Sufis of the Iraqi school.

CONCLUSION. From what we have discussed above, it is known that the school of mysticism of Baghdad was called "Sufi", and its mystics were called "Sufi", but these terms were not applied to the mysticism of Mowarounnahr and Khurasan until the 10th century. There were some disagreements and arguments between these schools. Probably for this reason, "Sufi" term was not in circulation in these regions in the early days.

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